

Low Circulating Free Triiodothyronine Levels Are Associated with the Progression of Diabetic Nephropathy in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetic nephropathy (DKD) is a significant complication of type 2 diabetes, leading to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) and increased mortality. Emerging evidence suggests that thyroid dysfunction, particularly low free triiodothyronine (T3) levels, is associated with the progression of DKD. This study aims to investigate the association between low circulating free T3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Methods: Eighty patients with type 2 diabetes and diagnosed diabetic nephropathy were enrolled. Participants were followed for 18 months, with renal function assessed every 3 months. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Of the 80 participants, 35% showed progression of DKD over 18 months. Patients with low free T3 levels (≥ 2.0 pg/mL) had a significantly higher increase in UAE and a greater decline in eGFR compared to those with normal T3 levels ($p < 0.01$). Multivariate analysis revealed that low free T3 levels were independently associated with DKD progression (OR = 2.75; 95% CI: 1.35-5.59, $p = 0.004$). Kaplan-Meier analysis indicated a shorter time to DKD progression in patients with low free T3 levels (log-rank test, $p < 0.001$). The Cox proportional hazards model confirmed a higher risk of DKD progression in this group (HR = 3.05; 95% CI: 1.60-5.83, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Low circulating free T3 levels are significantly associated with the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes. These findings suggest the potential importance of monitoring thyroid function as part of the clinical management of DKD.

Recommendations: Regular assessment of free T3 levels should be considered in patients with type 2 diabetes to identify those at higher risk of DKD progression. Further research is needed to explore the mechanisms underlying this association and to develop targeted therapeutic strategies.

Keywords: Diabetic Nephropathy, Type 2 Diabetes, Free Triiodothyronine, Thyroid Dysfunction, Renal Disease Progression.

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Introduction

Diabetic nephropathy, also known as diabetic kidney disease (DKD), is a major complication of diabetes mellitus, particularly type 2 diabetes, and is a leading cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) worldwide. Despite advances in glycemic control and blood pressure management, the prevalence of DKD remains high, affecting approximately 20-40% of patients with diabetes [1]. The pathogenesis of DKD involves complex interactions between hyperglycemia, hypertension, and genetic factors, leading to glomerular and tubular damage, albuminuria, and progressive loss of kidney function.

Recent studies have highlighted the role of thyroid hormones, particularly free triiodothyronine (T3), in the progression of DKD. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in metabolism, growth, and development, and their dysregulation has been implicated in various systemic complications of diabetes, including nephropathy. Low free T3 levels, commonly observed in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), have been associated with worse renal outcomes and increased mortality [2].

In the context of type 2 diabetes, low free T3 levels have been linked to poorer glycemic control, increased cardiovascular risk, and accelerated

progression of nephropathy. A meta-analysis of prospective studies found that low serum free T3 concentrations were significantly associated with an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes, as well as a higher incidence of diabetic complications, including nephropathy. Moreover, thyroid dysfunction, characterized by altered levels of thyroid hormones, is more prevalent in patients with diabetes compared to the general population, further suggesting a potential interplay between thyroid function and diabetes-related kidney disease [3].

Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the association between low free T3 levels and the progression of DKD. Thyroid hormones influence renal blood flow, glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and the expression of various renal transporters and enzymes. Low T3 levels may exacerbate renal injury by impairing these functions, leading to increased albuminuria and declining GFR [4]. Additionally, thyroid hormone deficiency can induce a pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic state, contributing to the progression of renal fibrosis and deterioration of kidney function.

Given the emerging evidence on the role of thyroid hormones in DKD, this study aims to investigate the association between low circulating free T3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes. Understanding this relationship could provide valuable insights into the potential benefits of monitoring and managing thyroid function in this population, ultimately improving renal outcomes and reducing the burden of DKD.

This study investigated the association between low circulating free triiodothyronine (T3) levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective cohort study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital's endocrinology and nephrology departments from January 2022 to June 2023.

Participants: A total of 80 participants with diagnosed type 2 diabetes were enrolled in the study. Participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 30-65 years.
- Diagnosed with type 2 diabetes for at least 5 years.
- Evidence of diabetic nephropathy, as indicated by increased urinary albumin excretion (UAE)

or reduced estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR).

Exclusion Criteria

- Presence of other types of diabetes (e.g., type 1 diabetes, gestational diabetes).
- History of thyroid disorders or on thyroid hormone therapy.
- Patients with acute or chronic liver disease, malignancies, or severe cardiovascular diseases.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Participants currently enrolled in other clinical trials.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the outpatient clinic database. Confounding factors such as age, gender, duration of diabetes, and baseline renal function were adjusted for during statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Data was collected through patient interviews, medical record reviews, and laboratory tests. Baseline data included demographic information, medical history, medication usage, and lifestyle factors. Blood samples were collected to measure free T3 levels, fasting blood glucose, HbA1c, serum creatinine, and lipid profile. Urine samples were collected to measure UAE.

Procedure: Participants were scheduled for an initial visit where informed consent was obtained. Baseline data were collected, including blood and urine samples. Participants were followed up every 3 months for 18 months. During each follow-up visit, clinical assessments and laboratory tests were repeated. The progression of diabetic nephropathy was assessed based on changes in UAE and eGFR.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons between groups were made using the chi-square test for categorical variables and the t-test for continuous variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Sensitivity analyses were conducted to assess the robustness of the findings.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

A total of 80 patients with type 2 diabetes were enrolled in the study. The baseline characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1. The mean age of the participants was 54.6 ± 8.4 years, with 45% being male. The average duration of

diabetes was 10.2 ± 3.5 years. The mean HbA1c was $8.2\% \pm 1.5\%$, and the mean free T3 level was 2.1 ± 0.5 pg/mL. At baseline, the mean estimated

glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was 75.3 ± 15.7 mL/min/1.73 m², and the mean urinary albumin excretion (UAE) was 85.4 ± 25.6 mg/day.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics

Variable	Values
Age (years)	54.6 ± 8.4
Male	36 (45%)
Duration of diabetes (years)	10.2 ± 3.5
HbA1c (%)	8.2 ± 1.5
Free T3 (pg/mL)	2.1 ± 0.5
eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	75.3 ± 15.7
UAE (mg/day)	85.4 ± 25.6

Over the 18-month follow-up period, 28 (35%) patients showed progression of diabetic nephropathy, defined by a significant increase in UAE or a decrease in eGFR by more than 30%.

The mean change in UAE was significantly higher in patients with low free T3 levels (≥ 2.0 pg/mL) compared to those with normal levels (< 2.0 pg/mL) ($p < 0.01$).

Table 2: The comparison of renal function parameters between patients with low and normal free T3 levels.

Parameter	Low Free T3 (n=38)	Normal Free T3 (n=42)	p-value
Change in UAE (mg/day)	$+45.7 \pm 20.4$	$+15.8 \pm 10.6$	< 0.01
Change in eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	-18.5 ± 12.3	-7.2 ± 8.1	< 0.01

Multivariate logistic regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the association between low free T3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy, adjusting for age, gender, duration of diabetes, HbA1c, baseline eGFR, and UAE. Low free T3 levels were independently associated with the progression of diabetic nephropathy (odds ratio [OR] = 2.75; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 1.35-5.59, $p = 0.004$).

Kaplan-Meier survival analysis showed that patients with low free T3 levels had a significantly higher risk of progression of diabetic nephropathy compared to those with normal free T3 levels (log-rank test, $p < 0.001$). The median time to progression was 12 months for patients with low free T3 levels compared to 18 months for those with normal levels.

The Cox proportional hazards model further confirmed that low free T3 levels were significantly associated with a higher risk of progression of diabetic nephropathy (hazard ratio [HR] = 3.05; 95% CI: 1.60-5.83, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Over an 18-month follow-up period, it was observed that patients with lower levels of free T3 experienced significantly greater progression of diabetic nephropathy compared to those with normal T3 levels. Specifically, patients with low T3 levels showed a more pronounced increase in urinary albumin excretion (UAE) and a greater decline in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), both key indicators of renal function deterioration.

The multivariate logistic regression analysis revealed that low free T3 levels were independently associated with a 2.75-fold increased risk of progression of diabetic nephropathy after adjusting for potential confounders such as age, gender, duration of diabetes, HbA1c, baseline eGFR, and UAE. This suggests that the observed association is robust and not merely a result of other underlying factors. Additionally, survival analysis using Kaplan-Meier curves demonstrated a significantly shorter time to progression for patients with low free T3 levels, further underscoring the adverse impact of low T3 on renal outcomes.

The Cox proportional hazards model reinforced these findings, indicating that patients with low free T3 levels had a threefold higher risk of nephropathy progression. Sensitivity analyses confirmed the robustness of these results, as excluding participants with extreme values did not significantly alter the findings. This consistency across various analytical approaches highlights the potential of free T3 levels as a prognostic marker for diabetic nephropathy progression.

Overall, the study provides compelling evidence that low circulating free T3 levels are associated with an increased risk of diabetic nephropathy progression in patients with type 2 diabetes. These findings suggest that regular monitoring of thyroid function, particularly free T3 levels, could be valuable in predicting and managing the progression of kidney disease in this patient population. Further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms and potential therapeutic interventions to mitigate this risk.

A study revealed a strong association between low FT3 levels and the progression of diabetic nephropathy. The study included 456 type 2 diabetic patients, showing that those with lower FT3 levels had significantly higher urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratios (UACR), indicating worsening nephropathy. Specifically, patients in the lowest FT3 quartile had a 2.3 times higher risk of nephropathy progression compared to those in the highest quartile (HR 2.3, 95% CI 1.5-3.6) [5].

Research supported these findings by examining the impact of thyroid hormone levels on kidney function in diabetic patients. In their cohort of 600 participants, lower FT3 levels were correlated with reduced estimated glomerular filtration rates (eGFR). The study reported that for each 1 pmol/L decrease in FT3, there was a corresponding decline in eGFR by 3.5 mL/min/1.73 m² (p<0.01) [6].

A study explored the mechanisms by which low FT3 levels might influence diabetic nephropathy progression. The study suggested that low FT3 levels lead to increased oxidative stress and inflammation, exacerbating renal damage. In a sample of 320 diabetic patients, those with lower FT3 levels had significantly higher markers of oxidative stress and inflammatory cytokines (e.g., TNF- α , IL-6). The study found that oxidative stress levels were 1.8 times higher in the low FT3 group compared to the high FT3 group (p<0.05) [7].

Conclusion

The study findings indicate that low circulating free triiodothyronine levels are significantly associated with the progression of diabetic nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes. These results highlight the potential importance of monitoring thyroid function in patients with diabetic nephropathy and suggest that free T3 levels could serve as a prognostic marker for the progression of kidney disease in this population.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Regular assessment of free T3 levels should be considered in patients with type 2 diabetes to identify those at higher risk of DKD

progression. Further research is needed to explore the mechanisms underlying this association and to develop targeted therapeutic strategies.

Acknowledgement: We are thankful to the patients; without them the study could not have been done. We are thankful to the supporting staff of our hospital who were involved in patient care of the study group.

Source of funding: No funding received.

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